

Derivation and Validation of a Mechanically Consistent Continuum Damage Model for Brittle Composite Materials

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Motivation

A generic framework to model the stiffness degradation of a brittle material reads [1]:

$$\phi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D}) = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} : \mathbb{C}^0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \phi^d(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D})$$

with \mathbb{A} a second rank symmetric damage tensor \mathbf{D}

• The damage effect $\phi^d(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D})$:

- Is often formulated using the effective stress concept together with different equivalence requirements, examples are [2]:

$$\mathbb{C} = \mathbb{M}(\mathbf{D})^{-1} : \mathbb{C}^0 : \mathbb{M}(\mathbf{D})^{-T} \quad (\text{Energy equivalence})$$

$$\mathbb{C} = \mathbb{M}(\mathbf{D})^{-1} : \mathbb{C}^0 \quad (\text{Strain equivalence})$$

- Problem: The latter is not symmetric and there is no rigorous way to choose $\mathbb{M}(\mathbf{D})$
- A more sophisticated model for brittle materials [1]:

$$\mathbb{M}(\mathbf{D}) = \frac{\xi}{2} (\mathbf{1} \otimes \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D} \otimes \mathbf{1}) + \frac{1-\xi}{2} [\mathbf{1} \bar{\otimes} \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D} \bar{\otimes} \mathbf{1}]_s$$

Most of the damage effect models violate the damage growth criterion [3]:

An increase in damage should always lead to a decrease in strain energy (or equivalently a decrease in stiffness):

$$\phi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D}) \geq \phi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D} + d\mathbf{D}), \quad \forall \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \forall d\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{D} \in \text{PSym}$$

Derivation of a mechanically consistent damage effect

Derivation of a mechanically consistent damage effect fulfilling the damage growth criterion by applying the theory of invariant tensor functions [4]:

Starting Point:

- The damage effect $\phi^d(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D})$ is a polynomial with degree two in \mathbf{D} and has only quadratic terms in $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$
- It is assumed that the undamaged material has an orthotropic symmetry
→ Damage effect $\phi^d(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D})$ with 145 independent material parameters

The Reduction Process:

- Reduce damage to in-plane damage $\mathbf{D} = D_{11} \mathbf{e}_1 \otimes \mathbf{e}_1 + D_{22} \mathbf{e}_2 \otimes \mathbf{e}_2$
- Fulfil the damage growth criterion [3]

$$\phi_{\text{iso}}^d(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \mathbf{D}) = \xi_0 \text{Tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2 \mathbf{D}) + \text{Tr}(\mathbf{D}) [\xi_1 \text{Tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2) + \xi_2 \text{Tr}(\mathbf{M}^2 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2) \dots \\ \dots + \xi_3 \text{Tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})^2 + \xi_4 \text{Tr}(\mathbf{M} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon})^2 + \xi_5 \text{Tr}(\mathbf{M}^2 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2)]$$

- Only 6 material parameters ξ_0, \dots, ξ_5 left
- With a slight loss in accuracy further reduction to 1 material parameter ξ_0 possible

Fig 1: Model from Chaboche and Maire [1]: regions with a positive (red) and negative (green) damage growth rate. Example for isotropic \mathbb{C}^0 with $\xi = 1, \nu = 0.3$ (left) and $\xi = 0.5, \nu = 0.499$ (right)

Results

Fig 2: Model validation using virtual test data from a homogenization approach assuming a dilute crack concentration in a homogeneous anisotropic matrix (left), damage deactivation if crack set i ($g_i \leq 0$) is closed (right).

Outlook

In the next step the model will be further adapted and validated for the application to brittle composite materials (Ceramic Matrix Composites):

- Complement the model with a damage evolution
- Validation by experimental data acquired by ultrasonic measurements on damaged samples

References

- [1] Chaboche J.L., and Maire J.F. *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 6 (2002), 131-145.
- [2] Coredebois, J.-P., and Sidoroff, F. *Mécanique des Solides Anisotropes*, 295 (1982), 761-774.
- [3] Wulfinghoff, S. et. al., *Int. J. Solids and Struct.* 121 (2017), 21-32.
- [4] Zheng, Q., *Appl. Mech. Rev.*, 47 (11), 545-587.